

Location Tracking

● **Abstract:**

Location tracking technology has become an essential component of modern digital systems, enabling applications in navigation, security, marketing, and law enforcement. This review paper explores various location tracking methods, including GPS, IMEI-based tracking, and IP-based geolocation, analysing their accuracy, reliability, and limitations. The paper also highlights the ethical concerns and privacy implications associated with tracking technologies.

● **Introduction:**

Location tracking is the process of collecting and analysing data to determine the physical location of a person, object, or vehicle. This can be achieved using a variety of technologies, each designed for specific scenarios. There are various technologies and methods to track location. GPS (Global Positioning System) is commonly used for accurate outdoor tracking by leveraging satellite signals. IMEI numbers (International Mobile Equipment Identity) allow mobile devices to be tracked through cellular networks, even when SIM cards are replaced. IP address tracking estimates location based on the internet connection of a device and is often used in web applications. Additional methods include Wi-Fi-based tracking, which identifies location using known Wi-Fi hotspots; Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) tracking, suitable for short-range tracking with devices like beacons; and RFID (Radio-Frequency Identification), used for asset tracking and inventory management. Advanced techniques, such as cellular network triangulation and indoor positioning systems (IPS), further expand the scope of location tracking in diverse environments.[1]

Location Tracking using GPS:

GPS tracking is the surveillance of location through use of the Global Positioning System (GPS) to track the location of an entity or object remotely. The technology can pinpoint longitude, latitude, ground speed, and course direction of the target. [7]

Location tracking has been of great importance since World War II, when military planners realized its usefulness for targeting, fleet management, positioning, and navigation. Today, GPS has a wide range of other applications including tracking package delivery, mobile commerce, emergency response, exploration, surveying, law enforcement, recreation, wildlife tracking, search and rescue, roadside assistance, stolen vehicle recovery, satellite data processing, and resource management. Tracking methods are generally based on a moving object's distance, direction, or both. GPS consists of a network of 24 satellites in six different 12-hour orbital paths spaced so that at least five are in view from every point on the globe. The satellites continuously transmit military and civilian navigation data on two Lband frequencies. Five monitor stations and four ground antennas located around the world passively gather range data on each satellite's exact position. The receiver can determine the user's latitude, longitude, and altitude using GPS, once it has calculated the user's 3D position, the receiver can also calculate other useful information.[2].

GPS comprises of three "segments" namely, the Control Segment, the Space Segment and the User Segment. Correct functioning of these three segments leads to the precise and consistent working of the whole system. The Control Segment is also known as the main control centre as it is involved in the transmission to the satellites. The Space Segment is composed of a collection of satellites that orbits about 20,000 km beyond the Earth. The User Segment is composed of the receivers that listen to the satellites at any given time. [8]

Real time GPS tracking:

GPS real-time tracking is analogous to having a high-tech radar that constantly (updates you on the whereabouts of people, cars, or goods. The Global Positioning System (GPS), a smart network of satellites, is used to locate the exact coordinates of whatever you're tracking.[13]

Google Earth and Google Maps:

Google Earth is a very popular free software that provides maps by satellite images around the world [15]. Google Map is a version of Google Earth that shows the maps on-line using with a web server and a web browser. The program provides plug-ins for community to show objects in the program. Such objects are, for example, 3D objects of skyscrapers using Sketch Up software, pin objects to indicate a point of interest (POI), and line objects to show a track. To show

such objects, Google Earth utilizes its own programming language called KML (Keyhole Markup Language) [16] which is an extensible markup language (XML) that is written to describe how the objects are rendered. The KML-based objects can also be used with Google Map to show line and pin objects. In our proposed system, we employ Google Earth software and Google Map as our choices of track displays to show locations of vehicles

An example software Goo-Tracking):

A GPS tracking system called Goo-Tracking that is composed of commodity hardware, open-source software and an easy-to-manage user interface via a web server with Google Map or via Google Earth software. This system is developed in the King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok. The system includes a GPS/GPRS module to location acquisition and message transmission, MMC to temporary store location information, and an 8-bit AVR microcontroller. This system shows great stability and also robust message transfer protocol that most of locations are accurately acquired and transmitted to the server in real-time.[14]

Figure1: Block Diagram of GPS Tracking device: Goo-Tracking[14]

Location Tracking using IMEI (International Mobile Equipment Identity) Number:

A smartphone is a mobile phone with an operating system capable of performing tasks that are not feasible on a basic mobile phone. It has provided us convenience to do task we normally would do on our computer like email, shopping and

banking as well as providing the various way for entertaining like gaming, watching videos and movie and the social media which has brought people near to each other and increased the communication among the people.

The International Mobile Equipment Identity (IMEI) number is used to uniquely identify 3GPP1 (i.e., GSM, UMTS and LTE) and iDEN2 mobiles phones, as well as some satellite phones. The IMEI number is used by wireless network operator (GSM network) to identify valid devices over the network and to stop the stolen phone from accessing network IMEI number is put on Blacklist by network operator. The IMEI number of the mobile is used only for identification of the device over the wireless network and subscriber has only semi-permanent relation to the IMEI number.

Having smartphone or tablet stolen is a serious problem, as it compromises to individual privacy and security. So electronic serial numbers were created to give unique identification to mobile devices known as International Mobile equipment Identity (IMEI) and the MEID (Mobile Equipment ID-a super set of IMEI) of today. IMEI is unique to every ME (mobile equipment) and uniquely identifies an individual mobile station. The IMEI format is given by Telecommunication standardization authorities and structured by the BABT3 and structure of IMEI is specified in 3GPP TS 23.003. The IMEI (15 decimal digits: 14 digits plus a check digit). From 2004, the format of the IMEI is AA-BBBBBB-CCCCC-D. The model and mobile phone brand is represented by initial 8 digit portion of the IMEI/SV, Known as Type Allocation Code (TAC) and 7 remaining digits are defined by manufacturer (6 are serial number and D is the check digit).[3]

Location Tracking using IP Address:

Many online services such as search engines determine the location of users at city-level granularity by consulting IP geolocation databases, which map IP ranges to physical locations. This location information is then used for geographic personalization. [4] IP Geolocation is the process of obtaining the geographical location of an individual or party starting out with nothing more than an IP address. Geolocation is the identification of the real-world geographic location of an Internet-connected computer, mobile device, website visitor or other. IP address Geolocation data can include information such as country, region, city, postal/zip code, latitude, longitude and time zone.

The organisations that are responsible for allocating IP address is the Internet Assigned Number Authority (IANA) that allocates large blocks of IP addresses to the following five Regional Internet Registries (RIR) that serve specific regions in the world: AFRI NIC (Africa), APNIC (Asia/Pacific), ARIN (North America), LACNIC (Latin America) and RIPE NCC (Europe, the Middle East and Central Asia). These RIR's then allocate blocks of IP addresses to Internet Service Providers (ISP) who then allocates IP addresses to businesses, organizations and individual consumers. [5]

The foundation for geolocation is the Internet protocol (IP) address, a numeric string assigned to every device attached to the Internet. When you surf the web, your computer sends out this IP address to every website you visit. IP addresses are not like mailing addresses. Most are not fixed to a specific geographic location because IP addresses are Static. Knowing that a particular ISP is based in a particular city is no guarantee that you'll know where its customers are located. That's where geolocation service providers come in. Geolocation service providers build massive databases that link each IP address to a specific location. [6]

Real time User IP tracking:

It begins with user interactions on the client's website/application, triggering an API call to Azure services to retrieve their IP addresses with time stamp. Azure's robust infrastructure processes these requests efficiently. Subsequently, retrieved IP addresses are stored in Azure Storage within a CSV file. If the CSV file is non-existent, it is dynamically created with an IP address header. The data is then accessed and analysed in an Azure ML Notebook, where comprehensive data operations take place. This includes data cleaning and preprocessing to ensure high data quality and consistency. Statistical analysis techniques are employed to discern user behaviour patterns, session durations, and other pertinent metrics. Additionally, geolocation data is leveraged to map IP addresses, providing insights into geographical distribution patterns. Finally, data visualization techniques are implemented to effectively communicate research findings, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions. This methodology ensures a systematic and data-driven approach to understanding user behaviour and enhancing the applications performance.[9][10]

Algorithm:

Step 1: User Accesses Website:

- When a user accesses the website, the algorithm initiates.

Step 2: API Call to Azure Services:

- The website sends an API call to Azure services to retrieve the user's IP address and API process and returns IP address.

Step 3: Store IP Address in Azure Storage:

- The algorithm stores the user's IP address in Azure Storage. If the CSV file doesn't exist, it creates a new one and adds the IP address as a new record.

Step 4: Azure ML Notebook:

- Load the CSV file with user IP addresses from Azure Storage to Azure Notebook. Perform data cleaning and preprocessing.
- Conduct statistical analysis to identify patterns, trends, and geolocation information. [9][10][11]

Location Tracking using RFID:

RFID stands for Radio Frequency Identification and is a term that describes a system of identification [18]. RFID is based on storing and remotely retrieving information or data as it consists of RFID tag, RFID reader and back-end Database [19]. RFID tags store unique identification information of objects and communicate the tags so as to allow remote retrieval of their ID. RFID technology depends on the communication between the RFID tags and RFID readers. The range of the reader is dependent upon its operational frequency. Usually, the readers have their own software running on their ROM and also, communicate with other software to manipulate these unique identified tags [20]. Basically, the application which manipulates tag deduction information for the end user, communicates with the RFID reader to get the tag information through antennas. Many researchers have addressed issues that are related to RFID reliability and capability [19]. RFID is continuing to become popular because it increases efficiency and provides better service to stakeholders [18]. RFID technology has been realized as a performance differentiator for a variety of commercial applications, but its capability is yet to be fully utilised.[21]

Ethical Concerns and Privacy Implications:

While location tracking technologies offer numerous benefits, they also raise significant ethical and privacy concerns. The pervasive nature of tracking can lead to surveillance and data misuse, necessitating robust regulatory frameworks to protect user privacy. Transparency in data collection practices and user consent are critical to addressing these concerns.

Conclusion:

Location tracking technologies have significantly transformed various industries, including navigation, security, law enforcement, marketing, and logistics. By utilizing a combination of GPS, IMEI tracking, IP geolocation, RFID, etc. organizations can efficiently monitor assets, enhance user experiences, and improve operational efficiency. However, despite these benefits, privacy concerns and ethical issues remain major challenges, as improper use of tracking technologies can lead to data breaches, unauthorized surveillance, and misuse of personal information.

To ensure responsible and ethical implementation of location tracking, governments, organizations, and technology providers must enforce strong data protection laws such as GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation), CCPA (California Consumer Privacy Act), and PDPB (Personal Data Protection Bill) while promoting transparency in data collection. Additionally, future research should focus on developing more precise, secure, and privacy-preserving tracking techniques that balance functionality with user rights and data security. Advancements in AI-powered geolocation, blockchain for secure data storage, and privacy-enhancing technologies may offer solutions to mitigate risks while ensuring efficient and ethical location tracking in the years to come.

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